

EXPLORING TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF SCHOOL HEADS' SUPPORTIVE ATTITUDE AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THEIR PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This paper aimed to explore teachers' perceptions of school heads' supportive attitude and its perceived influence on their performance. The study employed a quantitative research methodology to acquire the perception of 350 public primary school teachers from 113 schools in the four Talukas of the district, Hyderabad, Pakistan, through a well-structured Likert scale questionnaire. Descriptive analysis was used to recognize and organize the key characteristics and patterns observed in the data. The outcomes revealed a consensus among the teachers regarding their head teacher's positive attitude. The head teachers are consistently perceived as supportive, motivational, dedicated, and respectful to the teachers. These characteristics of head teachers are essential to nurture teacher job satisfaction, inspire professional growth, and enhance the educational atmosphere. The paper recommends regular professional and leadership development programs for head teachers to further improve school management practices and promote a culture of collaboration and growth.

Keywords: School Leadership, Head Positive Attitudes, Teacher Perception of Head, Teacher Performance, School Environment.

INTRODUCTION

An educational institution has some key stakeholders, including students, teachers, the head teacher, parents, society, and departmental representatives. The institutional head has direct connections with all the stakeholders of the institution. The head teacher has an important role in influencing the overall environment of the institute (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2005). Likewise, the professional performance of the staff, including teachers, and the academic performance of students are influenced by the leadership of the head. The important attributes of a head's personality that matter most are their knowledge and skill levels, expertise, vision, and professional attitude towards matters (Bush, 2020).

Teachers are another key pillar of a school. Teachers' role is also important in nurturing students' motivation and performance (Stronge, 2018). Teachers who are satisfied with their job tend to perform better and ultimately cause better student performance (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011).

Teacher performance is the effective delivery of a teacher's duties and job responsibilities in the school environment. It encompasses a wide range of behaviors and activities that contribute to the overall educational experience (Marzano, 2007). A good teacher's performance means students learn effectively and feel motivated.

Teachers at the start of their career mostly suffer from personal and professional issues. They lack

self-confidence; hence, they struggle to face students. They face difficulty in balancing the workload. These issues negatively affect their overall professional performance and students' academic performance. Head teachers' mentorship can help them overcome these issues (Rabia & Parveen, 2024; Vikaraman, Mansor, & Hamzah, 2017).

Research Objective:

- To explore teachers' perceptions of school heads' supportive attitude and its perceived influence on their performance.

Research Question:

- To what extent do teachers perceive school heads as supportive, and how does this affect their professional performance?

Scope and Significance of the Study:

This study aims to explore positive attitudes of heads of public primary schools and their effect on the teachers' professional performance. The study collects quantitative responses using a structured questionnaire from 350 male and female primary school teachers. The insights are aimed at proposing head leadership development and effective school management practices for improved teacher performance and a positive school environment.

The novelty of this research lies in its focused investigation of the influence of head teachers' positive attitudes towards teachers on the teacher professional performance. The focused area in the context of public primary schools has received limited attention. The study contributes to the field of educational leadership by providing applicable recommendations to the school heads and the department to foster a supportive and productive working environment within the institutions. The outcomes of the study are valuable for education management, policymakers, and the training institutions guiding for strengthening head teachers' leadership, enhanced teacher motivation and satisfaction, and improved students' learning outcomes.

Limitations of the Study:

The study collected quantitative data from 350 male and female primary school teachers from the district of Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan,

through a structured questionnaire comprising 5-point Likert-scale items intended to measure teachers' perceptions of school heads' supportive attitude and its perceived impact on their professional performance.

Literature Review:

Impact of Supportive Attitude on School Environment

School environment denotes the overall physical and social settings and conditions within a school. It includes the physical infrastructure, academic atmosphere, and social environment of the school. School environment greatly influences the experiences and performance of the students, teachers, and other staff. A positive school environment is essential for effective education. A healthy school environment is essential to achieve long-term educational success. The role of the school head is very important in creating and fostering a positive school environment that supports teaching and learning. A highly skilled and devoted head can effectively lead this process (Krasnoff, 2015). A strong relationship between the head teacher and the teachers is an essential component of a healthy school environment. Teachers' involvement in decision-making builds a very friendly relationship between the head teacher and school teachers (Amina, 2015). It is the responsibility of school heads to make a positive school environment comprising physical, social, and academic environments (Murtedjo & Suharningsih, 2018).

Role of School Heads in Teacher Development

With the rising prominence of education over the course of time, the responsibilities of school head teachers have increased. Head teachers' strong relationships with teachers contribute to the teachers' professional growth, dedication towards responsibilities, and satisfaction with their job (Price, 2012). Heads should adjust their management style according to the situation. Heads should encourage adopting the latest teaching methods (Li, 2014). Institutional heads aiming to observe their teachers' satisfaction with their jobs, and improved performance, make and execute effective plans, adjust the school environment according to the requirements, and complement and reward staff (von Fischer & De Jong, 2017). Teachers like heads' professional

leadership skills, acknowledgment of their efforts, and support for their career growth (Karunanayake, 2013). On the other hand, the heads' impolite and unfair attitude decreases productivity and job satisfaction of the teachers (Akin CELIK, 2013).

Materials and Methods:

Research Design:

Population, Sample, and Sampling Technique:

Population		Sample Size		Sampling Technique	
Schools	Teachers	Schools 70%	Teachers 10%	For Schools	For Teachers
161	3671	113	367	Lottery Technique	Randon Sampling

All the teachers (n=3671) from 161 public primary schools in four Talukas, Latifabad, Qasimabad, Hyderabad city, and Hyderabad rural in the district of Hyderabad, shaped the population of the study. 70% of the population (n=113 schools), and 10% of the population (n=367 teachers) were selected as the representative samples of the study. The 70% as the sample for schools and 10% as the sample for teachers were based on the guidance from literature stating that for descriptive research, for a population around 150 to 200, a sample of 70% of the population, and for a population of over 3500, a sample of 10% of the population are adequate (Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2012). For the selection of sample schools, a lottery technique was used, and for the selection of sample participants, a random sampling technique was applied.

Data Collection Procedure and Tool:

The designated questionnaire was distributed to 367 primary school teachers from 131 schools in

This research employs a quantitative research design. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire to explore the experiences and perceptions of primary school teachers regarding the supportive attitude of their heads toward teachers and their perceived influence on their professional performance.

the four Talukas of district Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan, using the designated questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of an introduction portion guiding the respondents regarding the purpose of data collection and filling the questionnaire, the next portion contained Likert scale items to be rated on 5 scales (strongly disagree=1, disagree=2, neutral=3, agree=4, and strongly agree=5). These items aimed to gauge head teachers' positive attitude and its influence on teachers' performance. However, the study received n=350 questionnaires, which were correctly filled out.

Data Analysis:

Quantitative data collected in the form of Likert scale responses from 350 public primary school teachers were analyzed through descriptive analysis in the form of frequency and percentage to gain insights into exploring the influence of head teachers' positive attitude towards the teachers on their professional performance.

Results and Discussion:

Demographics:

Table 1. Demographic Statistics of Participating Teachers (N=350)

Category	Group	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	228	65.14%
	Female	122	34.86%
Age in Years	18 to 30	91	26.00%
	31 to 45	216	61.71%
	46 to 60	43	12.29%
Education	Bachelors	185	52.86%
	Masters	165	47.14%
Teaching Experience in Years	Up to 5	79	22.57%
	6 to 15	213	60.86%
	16 and above	58	16.57%

The analysis of demographic data revealed that; Almost two-thirds (65.14%) of the respondents are males, while females are 34.86%. This gap is justified as in the context of Sindh, Pakistan, male teachers are easily available and more inclined to participate in studies in comparison to females. Further, a significant majority of the participants (61.71%) are middle-aged adults (31-45 years), the young adults (18-30 years) also share a notable 26.00%, while the senior adults (46-60 years) only share 12.29%. Furthermore, the bachelor, and master's education respondents have almost equal representation 52.86%, and 47.14% respectively. Moreover, a substantial majority (60.86%) of the participants are mid-career experienced (6-15 years), the early careers (Up to 5 years) also have a notable representation (22.57%), while the highly experienced (16 and above years) share a representation of 16.57%. Overall, the demographic statistics suggest an adequately represented sample concerning gender, age, education, and teaching experience,

supporting the credibility and diversity of the outcomes.

Descriptive Analysis:

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive analysis, aimed at summarizing the key characteristics and patterns observed in the data.

Descriptive analysis summarizes and presents data in a concise and meaningful manner, providing a comprehensive synopsis of the basic characteristics of a dataset, and explores patterns and trends within the data. It plays a crucial role in the data analysis process by allowing researchers to gain insights into the central tendencies, variability, and distributions of the variables under study. Further, descriptive analysis plays a crucial role in effectively communicating research findings by presenting data using tables, charts, and graphs (Ahmed, Chandio, & Naqvi, 2023).

HPA1: Head supports students to reach their everyday goals.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Heads' Perceived Support for Students to Reach Everyday Goals

Scales	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	42	12.00%
Agree	301	86.00%
Neutral	7	2.00%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	0	0%

Regarding the head's support to students to reach their everyday goals, a significant cumulative of 98.00% teachers showed agreement in the form of strongly agree, and agree. Notably, None of them disagreed with the statement, and only

2.00% remained neutral in this case. The results show a strong consensus among teachers concerning the supportive role of head teachers in helping students accomplish their daily goals.

HPA2: Head motivates every individual in learning new methodologies

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Heads' Perceived Motivation for Individuals to Learn New Methodologies

Scales	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	39	11.14%
Agree	301	86.00%
Neutral	10	2.86%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	0	0%

Concerning the head's motivation for individual teachers in learning new methodologies, a momentous collective of 97.14% responding teachers exhibited agreement in the form of

strongly agree, and agree. Particularly, no teachers showed disagreement with the statement, and only a small percentage, 2.00% remained neutral in this case. The results show a strong harmony

among teachers concerning the head's role as a motivator for individual teachers, motivating them to learn new teaching methodologies.

HPA3: Head helps to face the challenges in the field.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for Heads' Perceived Support in Facing Challenges

Scales	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	53	15.14%
Agree	294	84.00%
Neutral	3	0.86%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%

With reference to the head's support for teachers facing challenges, a remarkable accumulation of 97.14% respondents agreed in the form of strongly agree, and agree. Notably, no respondent disagreed with the statement, and nearly 1

percent stayed neutral in this case. The results exhibit a solid accord among responding teachers regarding the head's supportive attitude when it comes to helping staff overcome professional challenges.

HPA4: Head works hard for the prosperity of the staff.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for Heads' Hard Work for the Prosperity of the Staff

Scales	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	39	11.14%
Agree	311	88.86%
Neutral	0	0%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%

Referring to the head's hard work for the success of the staff, all the teachers (100%) expressed agreement with the statement in the form of strongly agree, and agree. Interestingly, none of

the responding teachers disagreed or remained neutral. This complete consent implies that head teachers are perceived as highly devoted to the professional growth and well-being of their staff.

HPA5: Head deals with every situation in a polite and well-behaved way.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for Heads' Polite Dealing with Every Situation

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	39	11.14%
Agree	311	88.86%
Neutral	0	0%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly disagree	0	0%

Regarding the head's polite and professional behavior in dealing with every situation, all the teachers (100%) expressed agreement with the statement in the form of strongly agree, and agree. Interestingly, none of the teachers disagreed or stayed neutral. This whole agreement among teachers indicates that head

teachers are perceived as respectful and professional in dealing with various situations. Across all five indicators of head teachers' positive attitude, the responses reflect a clear and consistent acknowledgement of positive leadership characteristics among head teachers. The Extensive agreement and absence of disagreement suggest that head teachers are perceived as supportive, motivational, committed, and respectful leaders. These

qualities are essential for nurturing teacher satisfaction, encouraging professional growth, and ultimately enhancing the educational environment.

Conclusion:

This paper investigated the perceived positive attitude of head teachers and its impact on the professional performance of the public primary school teachers. The outcomes of the study revealed that the teachers consistently perceive head teachers' attitude as positive. They perceive the head teachers as supportive, helpful, motivational, devoted, and polite. These positive perceptions are closely associated with enhanced teachers' self-confidence, motivation, devotion, and job satisfaction. The findings highlight that a positive, inspiring, and respectful leadership approach by head teachers contributes significantly to a productive school environment and improved teacher performance.

Recommendations:

In connection with the findings, the study recommends;

Leadership Development: Arrange regular leadership and professional development programs for head teachers for enhanced personal and management skills.

Mentorship Culture: Encourage a mentorship culture in the school to support new and struggling teachers.

Collaborative Environment: Promote collaborative practices among school staff to maintain a positive and supportive working atmosphere within schools.

Policy Support: Recognize the role of positive leadership attitude in institutional effectiveness and reflect it in educational management strategies.

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